

Canadian Open Data Experience (CODE)

Description

The Canadian Open Data Experience (CODE), sponsored by the Government of Canada, hosts an annual open data competition where developers are invited to use open source data from the federal government to develop apps for smartphones and other portable electronic devices. Open source data is available through a licensing framework developed by the Government of Canada that is very similar to Creative Commons licensing tools. In 2014, over 900 developers submitted projects to the Canada Codes! 2014 competition. Winning apps included Canadian Travellers, an app that uses data sets from the Canadian Border Services Agency and Foreign Affairs and International Development to advise travellers of issues that may affect their safety and security while travelling abroad.

Other apps included Squalid Salad, an app using data from the Public Health Agency of Canada, designed to identify and address key areas in homes where common injuries occur to adults and children, intent on risk reduction and making the home safer. newRoots is designed to match new immigrants to cities where social and economic conditions are most likely support their integration into Canadian society. Data sets from multiple government departments are used to supply economic information, census statistics, labour market data and housing rental costs into an easy-to-use format.

The competition is part of a larger Government of Canada initiative to increase access to federal data sets in an effort to improve government transparency, engage citizens more openly in the democratic process and foster innovation.

Economic benefits

CODE engages amateur developers, entrepreneurs, and innovators in a 48-hour competition to build an accessible and easy-to-use app that is of benefit to Canadians. As part of the process, finalists are connected with venture capitalist investors, provided with scholarship and training opportunities and assisted with starting their own business. The competition encourages innovation and economic development through investment in small businesses that capitalise on open data sets.

Health/social benefits

The CODE competition selects three general categories that participants can choose to focus their project on each year. Categories are related to social, economic, political or other topics of importance with the goal to generate viable solutions to complex problems that may easily span multiple government departments or ministries.

Supporting links

'Canada Codes! 2014' http://bit.ly/Winner_Showcase
Accessed 27 April 2016.

'48 hour hackathon invites techies to create apps with government data' http://bit.ly/48_Hour_Hackathon
Accessed 05 May 2016.